

A Vertically Polarized Gap Waveguide Array Antenna for Joint Communication and Sensing

Reza Gheybi Zarnagh*, Abolfazl Haddadi†, Andrés Alayón Glazunov*‡

*Department of Electrical Engineering, University of Twente, Enschede, The Netherlands

† Gapwaves AB, Gothenburg, Sweden

‡ Department of Science and Technology, Linköping University, Norrköping Campus, Sweden

* r.gheyzarnagh@utwente.nl, † abolfazl.haddadi@gapwaves.com, ‡ andres.alayon.glazunov@liu.se

Abstract—An array antenna utilizing gap waveguide technology has been designed for joint communication and sensing applications. The array comprises a 5×5 configuration of single elements, each generating vertical polarization. Each group of five vertical slots is combined into a single port, resulting in a 5-element linear array that allows horizontal scanning. The design features a multi-layered structure, with five layers enabling vertical polarization. The initial distribution layer guides electromagnetic waves, while the subsequent four slotted layers progressively rotate the electric field orientation. The $S_{11} < -10$ dB impedance bandwidth is from 75.9 – 84.3 GHz at broadside and from 77 – 83 GHz at 30° scanning.

Index Terms—Joint communications and sensing, gap waveguides, vertical polarization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Systems with communication and sensing capabilities are attracting attention in many emerging applications, especially for autonomous smart vehicles [1]. Instead of having two separate systems, designing joint communication and sensing systems by sharing hardware and spectrum is beneficial. An integrated system also benefits from the mutual sharing of information for improved performance [2]. However, the coupling of communication and sensing signal paths and potential interference between beamforming fields of antennas will remain an issue. From a hardware point of view, using orthogonally polarized antennas is a well-known method to decrease the potential self-interference (SI) between beamforming antenna patterns and even to decrease the coupling between antenna parts in jointly designed wireless systems. These advantages become particularly significant for joint communication and sensing systems (JCAS) when compared to single-polarized antennas [3], [4]. A dual-polarized multi-beam antenna based on printed ridged waveguide has been proposed for radar and communication systems in [5]. However, the limited impedance bandwidth obtained by the proposed structure diminishes the advantages of using the wide bandwidth available at millimeter Waves (mmWaves).

Millimetre wave (mmWave) antennas provide an excellent basis for integrating the functions of communication and sensing thanks to their wide bandwidth and compact profiles. Gap waveguide technology provides a solution at mmWaves to overcome the issues with dielectric and transmission losses. It ensures a high-gain solution by confining electromagnetic

Fig. 1. (a) Isometric view of the array antenna. Simulated E-field distribution in (b) vertical slot, (c) first cavity, (d) second cavity, and (e) horizontal slot.

Fig. 2. Active reflection coefficient of the array antenna when scanning at different azimuth angles.

wave propagation within its guiding structure. The vertical slots on the slot layer of gap waveguide antennas can easily be arranged with $\lambda_g/2$ inter-element spacing to generate horizontally polarized waves and to cope with the appearance of grating lobes [6]. Achieving vertical polarization with the gap waveguide antennas is challenging because in-phase exciting of the horizontal slots is not possible in $\lambda_g/2$ periods. To overcome the problem of exciting the horizontal slots, one solution is to deploy metallic posts near slots to alter the shape of the propagation mode locally. Still, due to the obtained narrow impedance bandwidth, the solution does not look promising [7].

This paper proposes a solution for vertical polarization with

Fig. 3. Simulated E-plane patterns of the antenna for co-polarized and cross-polarized modes were analyzed at frequencies of 77, 78, and 79 GHz.

Fig. 4. Simulated H-plane patterns of the antenna for co-polarized and cross-polarized modes were analyzed at frequencies of 77, 78, and 79 GHz.

Fig. 5. Azimuth scanning at 5° step at 78 GHz.

the ridge gap waveguide antenna. The vertical polarization complements the horizontal polarization used in jointly designed communication and sensing systems. The following sections show the proposed antenna's design process and optimized results.

II. ARRAY ANTENNA DESIGN

This section outlines the design process of the vertically polarized array antenna. The CST Microwave Studio simulation software is utilized to simulate and optimize the proposed array antenna numerically. The antenna comprises a distribution layer to guide electromagnetic waves and four slotted layers that enable vertical polarization. These slotted layers convert horizontal polarization in the first layer to vertical polarization in the last. The first slotted layer features vertical slots, the final slotted layer includes horizontal slots, and the intermediate cavity layers rotate the electric field components by 90° total, with each cavity layer providing a 45° rotation. The antenna structure, slot layouts in different layers, and simulated electric field distribution in the slots are depicted in Fig. 1. The first slotted layer with vertical slots creates electric field components in the horizontal direction, and the cavity layers rotate these components by 45° each. Tapered slots and cavities help achieve lower side lobe levels.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

Fig. 2 shows the active beam reflection coefficients for the array antenna when the antenna beam scans to different azimuth plane angles. At broadside, the antenna operates in the 75.9 – 84.3 GHz frequency band, offering a 8.4 GHz $S_{11} < -10$ dB impedance bandwidth. At a 30° scanning angle, due to out-of-phase excitation at each port, the bandwidth reduces to cover the frequency band from 77 – 83 GHz. The simulated E- and H-plane radiation patterns at 77, 78, and 79 GHz are shown in Fig. 3 and 4, respectively. The scanning capability of the antenna in the azimuth plane is shown in Fig. 5, and because of radiating horizontal slots, the scanning angle is limited to $\pm 35^\circ$.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the simulation results, i.e., the scanning performance within $\pm 35^\circ$ and scanning impedance bandwidth from 77–83 GHz, we may conclude that the proposed array antenna is a good candidate for short-range joint communication and sensing (JCAS) systems. This antenna and an orthogonally polarized antenna enhance isolation due to self-interference, which is essential for JCAS operation. The bandwidth and scanning performance of the proposed array are notably good in the operating frequency band. Moreover, another important application of the proposed antenna is a high-gain fixed beam antenna radiating at the broadside.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been funded by the H2020-MSCA Project 955629 ITN-5VC. We also appreciate funding from the EL-LIIT strategic research environment (<https://elliit.se/>).

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Kumari, J. Choi, N. G. Prelcic, and R. W. Heath Jr., "IEEE 802.11ad-based radar: An approach to joint vehicular communication-radar system," 2017, in *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 67, no. 4, pp. 3012–3027, Apr. 2018.
- [2] N. González-Prelcic, R. Méndez-Rial and R. W. Heath, "Radar aided beam alignment in MmWave V2I communications supporting antenna diversity," 2016 Information Theory and Applications Workshop (ITA), La Jolla, CA, USA, 2016, pp. 1-7.
- [3] A. Bagheri, J. Petersson, A. Haddadi and A. A. Glazunov, "A $\pm 45^\circ$ Dual-Polarized Antenna for 5G mmWave Applications Based on Gap Waveguide Technology," 2019 International Symposium on Antennas and Propagation (ISAP), Xi'an, China, 2019, pp. 1-3.
- [4] B. Lindmark and M. Nilsson, "On the available diversity gain from different dual-polarized antennas," in *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 287-294, Feb 2001.
- [5] Y. Cao, G. A. E. Vandenbosch and S. Yan, "Low-Profile Dual-Polarized Multi-Beam Antenna Based on Pillbox Reflector and 3D-Printed Ridged Waveguide," in *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 70, no. 9, pp. 7578-7591, Sept. 2022.
- [6] A. Haddadi, C. Bencivenni and T. Emanuelsson, "Gap Waveguide Slot Array Antenna for Automotive Applications at E-Band," 2019 13th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP), Krakow, Poland, 2019, pp. 1-4.
- [7] Sehyun Park, Y. Okajima, J. Hirokawa and M. Ando, "A slotted post-wall waveguide array with interdigital structure for 45/spl deg/ linear and dual polarization," in *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 53, no. 9, pp. 2865-2871, Sept. 2005.